

The Adivasi Women: Slowly Pushed into Endless Abyss

Harsh Kinger*

Introduction

In recent times, the country has seen several struggles across the central Indian belt, specifically in the scheduled areas.¹ *Adivasis*² in Jharkhand and Chhattisgarh have started the *Pathalgadi Movement* which has now reached as far as the scheduled areas of Maharashtra. The *Adivasis*, particularly, a large number of *Adivasi women*, of Maharashtra also joined the long march from Nasik to Mumbai demanding the proper implementation of the forest rights act.

* **The author** is working with the *Adivasi* communities of Madhya Pradesh and Odisha during last few years.

The *Adivasis* of Gujarat also protested against the world's tallest statue. In all these struggles, women have participated in large numbers unlike other struggles. These struggles are clearly showing that the *Adivasis* across India are resisting the present paradigm of development. A paradigm which these communities think is destructive and reduces them to second grade citizens of this country.

In the discourse on development in our country today, one community that has been marginalized since independence is the *Adivasi* community. And within that community the women are further marginalized. In this piece, I intend to talk about the marginalization of the *Adivasi* women as a result of the imposition of this peculiar kind of 'development' in *Adivasi* areas of the country. The manifestation of this can be seen mainly in the change in agricultural practices and changes in the nature of forests – its management, governance and conservation on which these communities depend for their livelihood. I will also attempt to explain how these changes marginalize women from the market economy. I will draw from my experience of having worked with the *Adivasi* communities and also from other secondary sources.

The 2011 Census reports India to be the home to 104 million indigenous people, recognized variously as *Adivasis* (original inhabitants) though recorded as Scheduled Tribes under the Constitution of India. Most of these *Adivasi* communities are directly dependent upon their natural environment for their livelihood. The communities that I worked with are dependent on agriculture and forests for their livelihood. They practice shifting cultivation³ (also known as 'jhum' cultivation) and collect food and other non-timber forest produces for their sustenance and livelihood. Their diverse cultures and ways of life, evolved through *an intimate interface with their natural environment*, stand in stark contrast to that of the dominant mainstream. They know that 'they belong to the earth and not vice versa'. The *Adivasi* who practices agriculture does not look at food in isolation, but views the various life sustaining sources through which food comes into being as a living presence in their life and are part of their '*kutumb*' (a word used by 'kondh' *Adivasi* of Odisha for their community).

Agriculture and Women

In this food system, which is central to their way of life, the women play a very crucial role as majority of the work – both productive and reproductive is done by the women. The women are also knowledge carriers in these communities. The division of labour in an *Adivasi* household is skewed, where women perform the majority of functions, but is still slightly better than the

non-*Adivasi* household. What is important to understand is that women have an important role to play in deciding which crops to grow, which seeds to use and so on. The sowing season starts with a *bihan parb* (seed festival) in an *Adivasi* village where the whole community brings the seeds that they have saved and then they offer it to the “*Dahrani*” (earth goddess). The ‘*bejuni*’ (female priestess) of the village leads this *puja*. And the households also exchange seeds amongst themselves. These seeds are traditional seeds, which the households have been saving since generations. One can observe that women play a central role in this agricultural season. On an average, one finds that 25-30 crops are grown by a household, which includes millets, oilseeds, lentils, and tubers and vegetables. They observe mixed or poly-cultural⁴ farming with numerous food crops growing in tandem. This practice helps in improving soil health, as carefully planted legumes or nitrogen fixing plants (such as beans) accompany a crop of maize. As one crop uses up the soil nutrients, the legume crop replenishes them, ensuring that soil fertility is maintained. In addition, the ‘*khond*’ *Adivasis* access varieties of foods; edible leaves, fruits, berries, flowers, seeds, stems, tubers/roots, and mushrooms from the forest. Forest foods have the advantage that they are safe from contamination/adulteration, and are seasonally available all round the year; and are equitably accessible to all.

The knowledge of the various different kinds of seeds and their conservation, as well as agricultural practices, forest foods, processing and of preparing different food recipes is carried by women in these communities and transferred from one generation to the other. Similarly, even in other areas women do the maximum agricultural work and household work. And one finds a marked difference in the agricultural practices in *Adivasi* areas.

Now, in contrast to this, the kind of ‘modern’ agriculture that is being pushed by the government and the market, marginalizes the role of women in agriculture. By modern I mean agriculture which is ‘input intensive’ and depends solely on external inputs. Let us try to understand this by looking at only one crop. The recent trends in Rayagada (Odisha) show that the area under cotton cultivation has increased manifolds. This has changed the dynamics of agriculture. Now, the seeds are coming from the outside and are usually supplied by traders from Andhra Pradesh. These traders also provide them with fertilizers and pesticides. The whole package of practices changes when a family shifts from poly-cropping to mono-cropping of cotton. And it is usually seen that these traders enter the villages by establishing network with young males of the household. And this pushes women out of this whole transaction and reduces her role to a mere labourer.

One of the reasons why people have been shifting their choices to growing cotton is that the cash need in the household is increasing. This financial crunch faced by these *Adivasis* is real and needs to be addressed. But the cost these families end up paying is much more than the income or benefit. It is usually the women in the household who perform the function of spraying fertilizers and pesticides on the crop. This is often done at the cost of their personal health and family’s health. There have been cases in which because of excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides menstruation cycles are affected. In some cases, there have been premature deliveries of children, unheard of in this area before. So, what we see here with this shift is not just marginalization from decision making but also the cost of health the family and specifically the women pay. Over and above this, the cost of cultivation is high in cotton and the market keeps fluctuating so the risk is high. Most of the families we have interacted with have ended up getting into debts to pay the input cost back. Till date farmers suicide is unheard of in this *Adivasi* area of Rayagada as they have had no debts in the past. But if such a trend continues then unfortunately, there is a possibility that farmers in Rayagada may also resort to such a step. And this makes it clear that the women farmers pay the maximum cost in terms of her control over resources and also the health cost. There are similar and more complex issues involved with respect to other crops also.

Similarly, if we take a closer look at the trends of the role of women in agriculture, at a macro level, the NSSO and census data clearly shows that the gap between men and women in the work participation rate has grown considerably during 1999-2000 to 2011-12. The survey says that in 1999-2000, 41 per cent of rural working age women were engaged in agriculture which has fallen down to 28 per cent in 2011-12. This sharp decline, the report says, is

because of the reduction in rural employment which is mainly because of landlessness and labour displacing technologies. Agriculture as a sector itself is facing an existential threat today and the women in agriculture suffer the most because like men who migrate for opportunities in the urban areas, women do not have many opportunities to participate in the urban economy because of various socio-economic reasons. To summarize, I would say that in *Adivasi* areas, specifically women are reduced to daily wage labourers who neither have control over land and production nor do they have secure dignified livelihood as a wage labourer.

Forests and Women

The other important aspect of marginalization is with respect to forests. Forests are central to the lives of *Adivasis*. The community I worked with (the '*kondhs*') considered the mountains and forests as sacred. Gopinath Mohanty – one of Odisha's most famous writers has recorded an exchange he had with a census official in 1941. "What is your religion?" the official asked. And the *Kondhs* replied: "mountains". (Das, 2010) The official may have found this reply hilarious. But it shows how the *kondhs* value these mountains and forests. But, the Indian government, even in today's date, has not given up the colonial legacy when it comes to forests. It looks at forests only as resources to boost its economic growth. And the *Adivasis* who live in and around these forests are considered encroachers on their own land. Because of this difference in the world views (of the *Adivasi* and the state) there is a direct conflict between the *Adivasis* and the state and the market. And one of the manifestations of this conflict is the Maoist insurgencies in these states. There are also struggles, which we talked about in the beginning, in each of these central Indian states where *Adivasis* are fighting to assert their rights over their forests and land. One Statistic captures this unfortunate reality well. Out of the total number of people displaced by developmental projects around 60 per cent of them belong to the category of Scheduled tribes. And the consequences of loss of land and forests are grave for these communities and particularly for women.

Let us first try and understand how important the forests are for these communities. As a part of our work, we did a research in Odisha led by an ecologist Debal Deb titled "Food and Nutrition from Forest". This study compared different forest areas and mapped the diversity of food and non-food species that is available from the forest and also the amount of food that is harvested by an individual household. Often the value of uncultivated foods from the forest is overlooked and forests are not looked upon as sources of food by policy makers and thereby our discourse on food and nutritional security overlooks forests. This study fills this gap and it says that more than 25 per cent

of total cooked food comes from forest and the estimate would be greater if one accounts for uncooked forest foods. And some of these foods are nutritionally very rich and can be very useful in addressing the problem of malnutrition in these *Adivasi* areas. The other important finding is that the diversity of food and non-food species is particularly high in forests governed by the community themselves. And it is considerably low in the forests that are managed by the forest departments of the government. It is important to understand this fact because this helps us realize the extent to which the communities are affected when there are external interventions in the forests and its governance.

Women spend much more time in the forests as compared to men and know more about the biodiversity in these forests. From firewood and food for the house to fodder for the cattle, there are a variety of items that the *Adivasi* women are dependent on, from the forest. In our conversations with the women they underlined the importance of the forest by saying that ‘the fields that we cultivate may or may not give us good yields, but we can rely on the forests, where even if there is a forest fire, it gives us tubers (a variety of uncultivated tubers are available under the forest land).’ The forest, they say is more important than any other resource (even money) because it has survived us and we cannot trade it for anything. Research on this issue by leading researchers substantiates this point. Bina Agarwal, one such leading researcher finds that there is a direct relation between the participation of women and the quality of forest governance. And she says that the committees where there are more women prove to be better guardians of the forests and insist on stricter rules. In one of his books, Anupam Mishra (an environmentalist) notes that the implementation of the forest rights act, which gives control of forest land to the community, can and should

be looked at as a women's rights issue, as women specifically have more at stake when it comes to forests.

In the context of Odisha, the recent changes show that the nature of forest has been changing mainly because of the diversification of forests for serving nefarious commercial and corporate interests. Therefore, land rights and forest rights, particularly for women, is one of the most (if not the most) important issues. There are other ways in which the forest land is diversified. In Rayagada, a substantial proportion of the forest land has come under Eucalyptus, (Nilgiri) teak and cotton cultivation. This diversion is promoted by a nexus of corporate funded private agents, the forest department and several NGO's, which all promote these schemes as income generating schemes for the common man. We have discussed the problems associated with mono-cropping of cotton. The problem with eucalyptus and teak plantation is that both these trees don't allow much undergrowth around them. Moreover, according to some estimates Eucalyptus has been known to consume upto 40 litres of ground water a day which is very high as compared to other trees. This, therefore, impacts the ground water levels adversely and can thereby impact the availability of ground water in the nearby fields. Promoting Eucalyptus plantations has been banned by two state governments because of this very reason. Both eucalyptus and teak are not used by the *Adivasis* locally for their daily needs since their animals neither eat the leaves nor can it be used in preparing manure. These plants only serve the interests of the corporate sector for paper manufacturing and timber. The outcomes of introducing alien species in a bio-diverse forest are much more adverse for women.

In one of our workshops, the youth from the community identified that because of eucalyptus plantations, the women in the household have to walk much more than before just to collect water and firewood as the nearby water sources have started drying. This would inadvertently also affect the availability of food varieties, both cultivated and uncultivated. So, there would be a sinister increase in labour and concurrent reduction in the availability of food. And it goes without saying that this food stress affects women far more than any other member of the household as it is usually seen that women often go hungry to feed their children and men folk in cases of shortage of food. This in the longer run affects their health adversely. In other areas where there is more conflict between the forest department and *Adivasis*, research shows that, it is women who are blamed more for violating access rules (despite higher reported case of men). And importantly, in all this, women also lose control over the forest as they don't have a say in forest conservation. With the introduction of state and

market actors, the women in the village are marginalized in taking decisions pertaining to conservation and management.

Conclusion

From these observations made both, at a macro level and a micro level, it is clear that, *Adivasis*, specifically the *Adivasi* women, who have been central in the local economy as food producers and knowledge-bearers are being marginalized with the introduction of so-called modern agriculture and forestry. This is not to say that the women are very well placed, socially within their community. The women even within the *Adivasi* communities are affected by patriarchal norms. Historically, the gendered norms have forced women to carry out more work – both, agricultural and household. But the limited point is that the neo-liberal economy combined with the old patriarchal norms, together are further ensuring that the women cannot participate in the market economy and are also being marginalized in their own local rural economies. This piece also questions the kind of ‘development’ that we take for granted and is imposed upon the people at the margins and destroy their livelihoods to benefit a few.

I would like to end by showing my solidarity with the struggle and resistance of these women and their communities. The words of an *Adivasi* poet from Jharkhand, Jacinta Keraketta, truly capture the reality of this situation in which these communities are slowly being pushed, like into an endless abyss.

Ears of Paddy Tied & Bound by the Dam

Yet again Phulo’s heart
Is a sweltering, blazing desert
Burning within on its own hot sands
As she watches the sowing of seeds
After a light drizzle in the fields.

Holding onto a few scraps of paper,
Standing helpless on the banks of the dam,
In every rain, Salo’s mother
Searches frenziedly for her lost farmlands.

The city dazzles with lights shining bright,
All thanks to the building of the dam,
While she is startled at the very sight of her own shadow in the dark night
Cast by a flickering earthen lamp.

Today Soma starves,
For his fields are now massive reservoirs.

The cage of his ribs protrudes through his skin,
The innards shrink and shrivel within.
Now a dam to hold back the welling tears,
Now a dam to contain the seething rage,
These dams shall burst one day for sure,
When the boughs of the 'sakua'
From the hilltops, in rebellion roar,
Sweeping out powers that destroy and displace
And once again in the breeze will sway
The ears of paddy in their majesty,
Enclosed by mud mounds,...no more by dams.

Notes

1. Scheduled Areas are areas identified by the Fifth Schedule of the *Constitution of India*. Scheduled Areas are found in ten states of India, which have a predominant population of tribal communities.
2. *Adivasi* is the collective term for the indigenous people and it is used to denote that these people are the original inhabitants of India.
3. A form of agriculture, in which an area of ground is cleared of vegetation and cultivated for a few years and then abandoned for a new area until its fertility has been naturally restored.
4. Polyculture is agriculture using multiple crops in the same space, providing crop diversity, i.e. imitation of the diversity of natural ecosystems, and avoiding large stands of single crops, or monoculture.

References

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